

Prospects for evaluating the activities of educators in the higher education system

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Abstract. The article addresses the challenges of modernizing higher education in the context of informatization and digitalization in institutions worldwide. It explores various types, processes, and criteria for evaluating teaching staff performance. Additionally, the article highlights how modern electronic educational environments are reshaping the competencies of university teachers and driving the broader transformation of education systems.

Key words: Competence, teacher qualification, higher education, education modernization, e-learning environment, assessment, evaluation of pedagogical activity, evaluation criteria, commission.

I. Introduction.

The process of modernizing contemporary higher education is currently one of the most pressing issues in the education system. It involves improving the existing concept by introducing new methods for monitoring the quality and effectiveness of pedagogical activities. Enhancing the system of professional training and raising the qualification levels of university professors and lecturers is a crucial link in

managing the quality of the educational process. Today, advancements in science and technology demand a fundamental change in the expectations placed on education and its outcomes. Consequently, the development of new generation standards has become a significant task for educators. Until now, the state education standards have been based on a systematic-activity approach, which primarily focused on the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competencies. Therefore, it is necessary to establish new state education standards based on a competency-activity approach, aimed at self-development. This is because the essence of the current educational process in higher education is not centered on developing the needs and abilities of students but rather on delivering knowledge in an informational-verbal manner and forming skills and competencies.

Thus, the issue of developing effective methods for assessing the quality of education provided by university graduates, as well as evaluating the performance of university teachers, remains a pressing concern. It is advisable to refer to the experiences of foreign universities when assessing the activities of university professors and lecturers. Let's examine the main approaches to evaluating the work quality of teachers in universities in the United States.

Today, the U.S. education system is recognized as one of the highest quality and most prestigious in the world. Over 40 American universities are included in the TOP-100 of the world's most prestigious universities. Every year, more than 500,000 international students study in the United States, and nearly 75% of all living Nobel laureates teach at American universities. Therefore, it makes sense to review their approaches when organizing the monitoring and quality assessment of university teachers' activities.

In the U.S., the evaluation of teaching staff is carried out based on professional standards, according to which a good teacher should stand out for their ability to communicate effectively with students. This includes the clarity of their speech and the correct organization of the learning process. Additionally, a teacher must have a strong understanding of the subject matter, properly utilize educational materials, apply the topic effectively to students, and be able to capture and maintain students'

attention during lessons. The assessment of teachers' performance is conducted based on feedback from students, colleagues, and administrators.

Students are capable of accurately evaluating a teacher's communication skills, the value of the books they recommend, and the overall effectiveness of their teaching. Colleagues, on the other hand, assess the value and relevance of the curriculum content, the list of educational literature and materials used, the content of exam questions, the level of students' knowledge retention, the methods of knowledge assessment, and other related factors.

In American universities, the evaluation of teachers' performance is based on the following principles:

- The quality of education is determined by the academic abilities and professionalism of the teachers.
- The existence of clear criteria and a system for providing guidance to teachers on fulfilling their assigned roles is a key condition for the effectiveness of the evaluation process.
- Periodic assessment of the pedagogical staff's activities can enhance the moral integrity of professors and contribute to their professional development and effective performance.

The evaluation of teachers' activities is carried out in accordance with the following criteria:

Fig. 1 Evaluation of the teacher's activity

In American universities, evaluating the performance of professors and lecturers is a complex process. For instance, the evaluation system used by a particular department depends on the specific requirements of that university. In U.S. universities, regulations and guidelines require maintaining an official evaluation file for each teacher. Access to this file is restricted to university administration, which is responsible for making management decisions related to the evaluation of teaching staff. These files can contain any information regarding the teacher's performance, which may be used during the evaluation process.[10]

Evaluation Methods in the United Kingdom:

In the United Kingdom, teaching methods in universities are individualized, and the role of the teacher is of particular importance. Here, not only the "student-teacher" interaction is considered, but the assessment approaches are also focused on:

In the United Kingdom, the evaluation of teaching methods is not only focused on the effectiveness of individual teaching but also on the overall organization of the educational process by the entire teaching staff. The evaluation committee assesses the quality of students' learning experiences and their achievements. The pedagogical skill of the subject teacher is evaluated based on the students' level of knowledge and the results of their learning.

In British universities, the following academic positions are found in the field of education: professor, associate professor, senior lecturer, tutor, and lecturer. During the evaluation process, the committee examines the quality of students' learning experiences and their achievements. The results are compared with the tasks and assignments set by the subject teacher during the educational process. The criteria for assessing the quality of education in British universities generally include:

Figure 2: Criteria for Assessing the Quality of Education

In Germany, the evaluation of teaching staff is characterized by a practice-oriented approach, which is linked to several factors:

1. **Government Monopolistic Competence:** The government holds near-monopoly control over this area.
2. **High Standards and Reputation of Higher Education:** There is a high level of quality and prestige associated with higher education institutions.
3. **Teachers' Personal Interest in Renewal:** Teachers have a personal interest in enhancing their skills, implementing new curricula, modernizing educational content, and meeting contemporary demands.

The process of evaluating professional activities in Germany is based on three main categories:

1. **Teaching Performance:** Assessment of how effectively and efficiently teachers conduct their classes and engage with students.

2. **Research Contributions:** Evaluation of the teacher's contributions to research, including publications and other scholarly activities.

3. **Administrative and Institutional Involvement:** Consideration of the teacher's participation in institutional activities and administrative responsibilities.

These categories reflect the emphasis on both practical teaching effectiveness and broader contributions to the educational and research community.

Figure 3: The Process of Evaluating Professional Activities

Criteria for Assessing the Knowledge of Pedagogical Staff in Uzbekistan

In Uzbekistan, a number of decrees and resolutions have been developed to improve the training, retraining, and professional development of pedagogical staff, as well as to implement extensive reforms. For example, the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2909 dated April 20, 2017, "On Measures to Further Develop the Higher Education System," and the Presidential Decree No. PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018, "On Additional Measures to Improve the Quality of Education in Higher Education Institutions and Ensure Their Active Participation in the Comprehensive Reforms Being Implemented in the Country" are aimed at fundamentally improving the higher education system. These decrees focus on revising the training of personnel in line with the priority tasks of the country's socio-economic development, creating necessary conditions for training highly qualified

specialists at an international level, encouraging scientific research and innovation activities, and developing effective mechanisms for implementing scientific and innovative achievements into practice.

The Cabinet of Ministers' Decree No. 20 dated February 10, 2006, "On Approval of the Regulation on the Procedure for Recruitment of Pedagogical Staff in Higher Education Institutions on a Competitive Basis," outlines the criteria for evaluating the activities of pedagogical staff in higher education institutions. According to this regulation, the evaluation of pedagogical staff's activities is based on the following indicators, scored out of a total of 110 points:

Figure 4: evaluation of pedagogical staff

When evaluating the performance of teachers, it is crucial to first systematize the components of pedagogical activity and identify key factors based on systematic analysis. From this, it is important to emphasize that the effectiveness of assessing the activities of higher education institution teachers directly depends on determining the components, factors, and criteria of pedagogical activity. [8].

Descriptives Analysis Intrinsic Attitude Towards the English Language

Data collected have been both zed using descriptive methods and described (Table 1) to deepen understanding of what the participants witness as inherent aspects of their attitude disposition towards learning English. In the Table 1, the data

shows that the mean value of two factors (No.13, 16) is <2.50 and man values of remains 16 factors is >2.50. This research tells a story which explains that the intrinsic attitude towards English Language has a significant impact on the performance of bachelor students at Tashkent state University of economics. Such results are similar with that reported by the Norov et al. (2023) findings.

Table 1

Descriptive analysis of the questionnaire data (dimension 1 factors, n=140)

	Dimension 2 Factors	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	And the environment is great for English.	140	1	5	3.66	1.143
2	Foreign teachers occupy a high social status. The professor, who is a native English speaker, holds very high social status.	140	1	5	3.54	1.266
3	My company, along with a colleague and my parents, encourages me to practice speaking, listening, reading, and writing in English.	140	1	5	3.66	1.262
4	Indian English professors, I believe, should receive higher salaries than local professors to promote English language comprehension and learning.	140	1	5	3.64	1.235
5	I want to inspire my colleagues and classmates to expand their English knowledge.	140	1	5	3.74	1.185
6	I feel that English plays a very significant role in students' careers.	140	1	5	3.89	.994
7	My goal is to guide my peers in learning English to help them gain essential knowledge and skills.	140	1	5	3.58	1.200
8	I fully support mandatory English teaching at the university.	140	1	5	3.81	1.097
9	First priority: dismantle the policy of making College English a compulsory course for all.	140	1	5	3.60	1.186
10	And the environment is great for English.	140	1	5	2.36	1.176
	Valid N	140				

(Note: Strongly Disagree=1, Disagree=2, Neutral=3, Agree=4, Strongly Agree=5)

Results of Principal Component Analysis revealed the one factor (6) with eigenvalues around 1.0. Factor loadings and communalities were set lower than 0.400. The results are given in Table 2. This component explained 48.375% of the variance in total. Coefficients range from 0.425 to 0.524 for the ten variables.

Table 2

Analysis of variance and each factor's reliability demonstrated.

Table 3

Component	Rotation Sums of Squared Loading			
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Coefficients
1	4.937	49.371	49.371	.482
2	0.836	8.365	57.736	.428
3	0.796	7.964	65.700	.346
4	0.699	6.993	72.693	.458
5	0.655	6.546	79.239	.388
6	0.552	5.517	84.756	.904
7	0.532	5.321	90.077	.382
8	0.449	4.492	94.569	.547
9	0.437	4.374	98.942	.533
10	0.106	1.058	100.000	.470

External factors' rotated factor loadings

External factors' rotated factor loadings	
Dimension 2. Extrinsic assessment of English language	Factor load
6. I would like to encourage my colleagues and class fellows to learn English for more knowledge.	0.951
8. I would like to help my colleagues to learn English for advance knowledge and skills.	0.740
9. I support the current policy of compulsory College English education in university.	0.730
1. Speaking of English language environment is healthy and conducive.	0.694
10. The policy of College English as a compulsory course for everyone should be abolished.	0.685
4. My colleague's company and parents encourage me to speak, listen, read, and write in English.	0.677
2. Chinese English professors have high social status	0.654
5. I think HI English professors should be paid more than Native English professors to promote English language understanding and learning.	0.622
7. I believe that English language is/will play significant role for students' careers.	0.618
3. Native English professor have high social status.	0.588
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	

Policy Suggestions And Recommendations

The above conclusions show that the use of English is a suggestion for teachers who need to reconsider the needs and desires of local students. The most important thing for university policymakers is to focus on the idea that "quality

follows quantity" and try to provide a range of programs based on English language education. Student voice is critical to the development of local higher education institutions. Therefore, the authors of this paper recommend that the Ministry of Education of Uzbekistan continue to expand other EMI programs or attract local graduates to enter the current EMI programs.

II. Conclusion

Thus, in various countries, the evaluation processes of teaching staff are carried out through different methods, but their general approaches are based on the following:

1. The policy of evaluating pedagogical staff focuses on optimally utilizing their qualifications, fostering the need for professional development, and providing opportunities to meet this need.

2. The assessment of teaching staff qualifications abroad is built on important principles, such as respect for the teacher's personality and their civil and professional rights. It also emphasizes the necessity of a dual process in the development of programs and assessment criteria, requiring the involvement of teachers.

3. Evaluating the performance of teachers continually raises the standards of quality. In the USA and the UK, salaries are effectively linked to the quality of work as determined by evaluation results, with additional pay awarded for high-quality work.

4. A general approach to the quality of the educational process in universities is related to:

- Prioritizing the professional level of academic staff,
- The depth of academic and pedagogical knowledge among teaching staff.

Another criterion is the level of student intake, the organization of the educational process, and the use of modern equipment in higher education institutions, though the latter plays a significant but not decisive role.[9]

Additionally, when evaluating the performance of university teachers in different countries, the contribution of higher education institutions to enhancing cultural, historical, and national values is taken into account.

In conclusion, considering the closely interconnected components, factors, and conditions of pedagogical activity, the objective mechanisms for evaluating the performance of teaching staff in higher education institutions play a crucial role in training competitive personnel in the higher education system.

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